

Special issue

Article

The effect of a peptide adjuvant (YLQPRTFLL) on immune response against SARS-CoV-2 in Balb/C mice when vaccinated with saRNA LNPs

Reza Keikha 1,2, Ali Jebali 3*

1 Infectious Diseases and Tropical Medicine Research Center, Resistant Tuberculosis Institute, Zahedan University of Medical Sciences, Zahedan, Iran. 2 Department of Pathology, Faculty of Medicine, Zahedan University of Medical Sciences, Zahedan, Iran. 3 Department of Medical Nanotechnology, Faculty of Advanced Sciences and Technology, Tehran Medical Science, Islamic Azad University, Tehran, Iran. *Corresponding author information: Email: alijebal2011@gmail.com; Tell: 09900152139; Address: Department of Medical Nanotechnology, Faculty of Advanced Sciences and Technology, Tehran Medical Science, Islamic Azad University, Tehran, Iran.

Abstract: The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of Peptide Adjuvant on immune response against SARS-CoV-2 in Balb/C mice when vaccinated with saRNA LNPs combined with Peptide Adjuvant. It was found a high titer of IgG and IgA was seen ($P < 0.05$) after immunization of BALB/c mice with saRNA LNPs and saRNA LNPs+ Peptide Adjuvant. The combination of Peptide Adjuvant with saRNA LNPs significantly increased the antibody titer ($P < 0.05$). The high ratio of IgG2a/IgG1 indicated a Th1-biased responses in vaccinated mice. The secretion of IL-4 and IFN- γ in serum of vaccinated mice showed the significant differences in the mice vaccinated with saRNA LNPs and the mice vaccinated with saRNA LNPs and Peptide Adjuvant ($P < 0.05$).

Received: 27 February 2025
Revised: 10 April 2025
Accepted: 14 June 2025
Published: 19 June 2025

Citation: Keikha, R.; Jebali A. The effect of a peptide adjuvant (YLQPRTFLL) on immune response against SARS-CoV-2 in Balb/C mice when vaccinated with saRNA LNPs. *Special issue: Appl. Biosci.* **2025**, *1*, 1–9. <https://mdpigroup.com/journal/applbiosci/specialissue-applbiosci050004.pdf>

Copyright: ©2025 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Keywords: Self-amplifying RNA, Peptide Adjuvant, SARS-CoV-2

Introduction

Given the current and emerging viral diseases, the development of new vaccines is of great importance. Although many vaccines are based on inactivated viruses, there is a strong interest in novel approaches based on mRNA and saRNA. It should be noted that vaccines against COVID-19 have significantly benefited humanity, saving hundreds of thousands of lives (1-6). Certainly, new technologies such as biotechnology can provide more targeted immune responses through biomolecular design and engineering, helping us respond to a variety of mutated viruses [1-3].

It should be noted that the simplest platform is peptide vaccines, but they are not very efficient due to their small size. In addition, peptides have potential activities as adjuvants. Note that short peptides can be produced at scale using automated synthesis methods, while longer peptides and proteins can be produced recombinantly. Certain types of peptides, including surfactant-like peptides, lipopeptides (peptide amphiphiles), and amyloid-forming peptides, can self-assemble into nanostructures (nanofibrils, micelles, etc.) in aqueous solutions [4-6]. This could be beneficial for immunogenicity due to the provision of a high density of bioactive peptide units, potentially leading to improved antigen or adjuvant effects. Peptides can form self-assembled peptide nanoparticles (SAPNs),

and protein subunits can assemble into virus-like particles (VLPs) (**Table 1**) [7-9]. To date, few peptide-based vaccines have been used in the clinic, although several systems are in advanced stages of clinical trials [10, 11].

There are a number of candidate peptide vaccines for HIV and cancers, particularly melanoma, breast, prostate, and lung cancer. Cancer immunotherapies include those based on T-cell transfer, including CAR (chimeric antigen receptor) T-cell therapy, monoclonal antibodies, immune modulators such as interferons and interleukins, immune checkpoint inhibitors, and potential peptide subunit vaccines. Many of these approaches could benefit from peptides. For example, peptide-based molecules that are TLR (Toll-like receptor) agonists have attracted attention in cancer immunotherapy [12, 13]. The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of Peptide Adjuvant on immune response against SARS-CoV-2 in Balb/C mice when vaccinated with self-amplifying RNA lipid nanoparticles (saRNA LNPs) combined with Peptide Adjuvant.

Materials and methods

The preparation of saRNA vaccine

The saRNA construct was synthesized, sub-cloned in pHT01, and confirmed by Biomatik, Canada. based on our previous study [14]. The Norovirus GI sequence was incorporated in the saRNA design, because it can induce both humoral and mucosal response [15]. In the next step, the saRNA construct was cloned by a PCR reaction with Mastermix PFU DNA Polymerase (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Next, 10 ng purified DNA was first reacted with MEGAScript™ (Ambion, UK) for 1 h at 37 °C and then reacted with ScriptCap™ (CellScript, WI, USA) for 1 h at 37 °C. To encapsulate saRNA, 1 µg purified saRNA and one mL of ethanolic lipid mixture of DOSPA and DOPE (Merck, Germany) at a ratio of 3:1 were added and mixed for 5 minutes at room temperature. The mixture was purified by a centrifugation at 10000 RPM for 10 minutes. We performed replicates of formulations(at least n=3) to report full characterization [14].

Vaccination

BALB/c mice were vaccinated with:

- 1) 10 µg saRNA LNPs at weeks 1 and 3.
- 2) 10 µg saRNA LNPs mixed with 1 µg (Peptide Adjuvant) at weeks 1 and 3.
- 3) no thing as negative control.

The sequence of Peptide Adjuvant was YLQPRTFLL (Catalog number 25462) and provided from Sinazyst, Iran.

The injection route: subcutaneous, injection volume: 100 µL, injection instrument: insulin syringe, mice age: 6–8 weeks, sex: male, mice weight: 10-15g.

Antibody titration

A 96-well ELISA plate (Biomat, Italy) was coated with SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein Recombinant Antigen (Sigma-Aldrich) at 1 mg/mL for 24 hours at 4°C. After washing, the serial dilutions (1:1000, 1:500, 1:250, 1:125, 1:62.5, 1:31.2, 1:15.6) of serum samples were separately added to the ELISA plate and incubated at 37 °C for 1 hour. Finally, to obtain antibody titer, the OD of each well was compared with the OD of negative control. It is earned by comparison of Test-OD to cutoff of whines sample in each dilution

Table 1. The Viral Peptide Adjuvant Sequences.

Adjuvant Sequence	origin
SGPSNTPPEI	adenovirus Ad5 E1a protein
LEEKKGNYVVDH	B cell epitope from epidermal growth factor receptor class III variant
AKXVAAWTLKAAA	pan HLA DR-binding epitope (PADRE)
GQIGNDPNRDIL	universal Th cell epitope
QYIKANSKFIGITE	universal Th cell epitope
FNNFTVSFWLRVPKVSASHLE	universal Th cell epitope
AQYIKANSKFIGITEL	Th epitope
STDSCDSGPSNTPPEI	human adenovirus type 5 early region 1B CTL epitope
QLINTNGSWHIN	HCV E2 envelope glycoprotein epitope I
CGWVAGLFYYHKF	HCV E2 envelope glycoprotein epitope II
LMGYIPLVGA	HCV core TCL epitope
EGRAWAQPGYPWPLYGNEGL	HCV core Th epitope
AVGIGAVFLGFLGAAG and AVGIGAVF	HIV envelope glycoprotein gp41 fragments
LDKWASLWNWFNITNWLWYIR	HIV gp41 membrane proximal external region (MPER) epitope
ELLELDKW	HIV gp41 MPER epitope
RIQRGPGRAFVTIGK	HIV gp160 CTL epitope
SLYNTVATL	HIV glycoprotein CTL epitope
ILKEPVHGV	HIV Pol DNA polymerase CTL epitope
KQIINMWQEVGKAMYA	HIV gp120 Th epitope
NPNA (NANP) repeats	<i>P. falciparum</i> CS protein motif
YLQPRTFLL	SARS-CoV-2 T cell epitope
FLLNKEMYL	SARS-CoV-2 T cell epitope
FIAGLIAIV	SARS-CoV-2 T cell epitope
FVSEETGTL	SARS-CoV-2 T cell epitope
YVYSRVKNL	SARS-CoV-2 T cell epitope
SLVKPSFYV	SARS-CoV-2 T cell epitope
LAILTALRL	SARS-CoV-2 T cell epitope
WTAGAAAYY	SARS-CoV-2 HLA-binding epitope
GAAAYYVGY	SARS-CoV-2 HLA-binding epitope
RSIEDLLFDKV	common coronavirus spike protein sequence
KRSFIEDLLFNKV	SARS cleavage site sequence
ASTEK	SARS-CoV-2 RBD sequence
PKKS	SARS-CoV-2 RBD sequence
QLQMFGITVQYGT	MERS B cell epitope
YKLQPLTFL	MERS T cell epitope
YCILEPRSG	MERS T cell epitope
SVVNIQKEIDRLNEVAKNLN	SARS-CoV spike protein B cell epitope
RPQASGVYMGNLTAQ	lymphocytic choriomeningitis virus (LCMV) nucleoprotein T cell epitope
HGEFAPGNYPALWSYA	murine respirovirus nucleoprotein epitope
FAPGNYPAL	murine respirovirus CTL epitope

The secretion of IL-4 and IFN- γ

we used an ELISA kit to detect the level of IL-4 and IFN- γ . Briefly, 100 μ L of vaccinated mice were separately added to anti-mouse IL-4 (Southern Biotech) and IFN- γ (Southern Biotech) ELISA wells (Biomat, Italy). After 1 hour incubation at 37 °C, plates were washed with PBS and then 100 μ L of secondary antibody, including anti-mouse IL-4-HRP (Southern Biotech) and anti-mouse IFN- γ -HRP (Southern Biotech), was added. Then, 50 μ L of TMB (Sigma-Aldrich) was added. After 15 minutes, 100 μ L sulfuric acid (Sigma) was added and the OD of each well was read by a Spectrophotometer at 450 nm (BioTek Industries) and then the serum level of IL-4 and IFN- γ was quantified by standard curve [14].

Statistical analysis

All graphs and data are shown as Mean \pm SD. GraphPad Prism (version 8.4) was used to prepare graphs and statistics. Here, one-way ANOVA was used to indicate significance at $P < 0.05$ after post-hoc analyses, such as Tukey and Dunnett.

Results

The antibody titer

A high titer of IgG (**Figure 1a**) and IgA (**Figure 1b**) was seen ($P < 0.05$) after immunization of BALB/c mice with 1) saRNA LNPs, 2) saRNA LNPs+ Peptide Adjuvant. The combination of Peptide Adjuvant with saRNA LNPs significantly increased the antibody titer ($P < 0.05$). Here, the ratio of IgG2a/IgG1 was measured to find Th1-biased responses in vaccinated mice. The ratio of IgG2a/IgG1 was upper 1 in all study groups, indicating a Th1-biased response (**Figure 1c**). Also, we observed dose-response phenomenon.

The secretion of IL-4 and IFN- γ

The secretion of IL-4 and IFN- γ in serum of vaccinated mice (**Figure 2**) showed the significant differences in the mice vaccinated with saRNA LNPs and the mice vaccinated with saRNA LNPs and Peptide Adjuvant ($P < 0.05$).

Discussion

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of Peptide Adjuvant on immune response against SARS-CoV-2 in Balb/C mice when vaccinated with saRNA LNPs combined with Peptide Adjuvant. A high titer of IgG and IgA was seen ($P < 0.05$) after immunization of BALB/c mice with 1) saRNA LNPs, 2) saRNA LNPs+ Peptide Adjuvant. The combination of Peptide Adjuvant with saRNA LNPs significantly increased the antibody titer ($P < 0.05$). Here, the ratio of IgG2a/IgG1 was measured to find Th1-biased responses in vaccinated mice. The ratio of IgG2a/IgG1 was upper 1 in all study groups, indicating a Th1-biased response. Also, we observed dose-response phenomenon. The secretion of IL-4 and IFN- γ in serum of vaccinated mice showed the significant differences in the mice vaccinated with saRNA LNPs and the mice vaccinated with saRNA LNPs and Peptide Adjuvant ($P < 0.05$).

The immune system consists of innate and adaptive systems. The former utilizes cells such as neutrophils, macrophages, natural killer cells, and dendritic cells. The adaptive immune system relies on the activation of antigen-presenting cells (APCs) of the innate immune system.

Figure 1. The antibody titer. A high titer of IgG (a) and IgA (b) was seen after immunization of BALB/c mice with 1) saRNA LNPs, 2) saRNA LNPs+ Peptide Adjuvant. The combination of Peptide Adjuvant with saRNA LNPs significantly increased the antibody titer ($P < 0.05$). The ratio of IgG2a/IgG1 was upper 1 in all study groups, indicating a Th1-biased response (c).

Figure 2. The secretion of IL-4 and IFN- γ in serum of vaccinated mice showed the significant differences in the mice vaccinated with saRNA LNPs and the mice vaccinated with saRNA LNPs and Peptide Adjuvant ($P < 0.05$).

Antigen presentation involves the binding of antigen to the major histocompatibility complex (MHC) followed by the transport of the complex to the cell surface, where it can be recognized by the T cell receptor (TCR). The activated adaptive immune system utilizes B cells, T cells, dendritic cells, and antigen-recognizing antibodies. As mentioned above, the adaptive immune system produces T-helper cells that release cytokines to help other immune cells. T-helper cells differentiate into Th1 cells or Th2 cells. The cellular response relies on the former, and the humoral response involves Th2 cells.

This refers to the production of antibodies or antimicrobial peptides in the extracellular fluid (also known as antibody-mediated immunity). The activity of a vaccine may be improved by the use of an adjuvant, which is an additive that stimulates a stronger immune response. These have traditionally been based on minerals, particularly alum, but more recently, organic systems, particularly emulsions and liposome formulations, have been developed. Lipopeptides, particularly those containing the PamCS (palmitoyl-Cys-Ser) motif, can exhibit self-adjuvant properties, as discussed elsewhere [16]. Self-assembling peptides may have adjuvant activity that results from the formation of antigen depots, by targeting vaccines to APCs, or by improving priming of immune cells [17]. (58) Organic vaccine adjuvants have been discussed in a number of reviews [18, 19] and a review specifically on subunit-based peptide vaccine adjuvants is available [20].

The global COVID-19 pandemic caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus [SARS, severe acute respiratory syndrome] has stimulated extremely rapid and successful vaccines based on mRNA and adenovirus, etc [21, 22]. To date, peptide-epitope-based vaccines for SARS-CoV-2 have not been implemented, although a number of trials have been launched. Key to human cell recognition are glycoproteins that interact with the cellular receptor ACE2 (SARS-CoV-2 proteins have now been sequenced, and it has become possible to identify key regions involved in the binding of the spike protein to target cells, and these represent potential targets for therapeutic interventions.

Ethics approval for animal experiments

All experiments were under the guidelines of the National Institute of Health, the provisions of the Declaration of Helsinki, and the ethics committee of Zahedan University of Medical Sciences, Zahedan, Iran. (Ethical code: IR.ZAUMS.REC.1400.071).

Ethics approval for Human experiments

No human sample was used in this study.

Author Declarations and statements

- The authors confirm that all experiments were performed by ARRIVE guidelines and regulations of Zahedan University of Medical Sciences, Zahedan, Iran.
- We confirm that all experimental protocols were approved by Zahedan University of Medical Sciences, Zahedan, Iran.
- We confirm that all methods were carried out according to relevant guidelines and regulations of Zahedan University of Medical Sciences, Zahedan, Iran.

Consent for publication

Not

Availability of data and material

All data of this article is available based on the official request of researchers.

Competing interests

There is no conflict of interest.

Funding

This article was financially supported by Zahedan University of Medical Sciences, Zahedan, Iran (grant number: 10191).

Authors' contributions

(I) Conception and design: R.K and A.J, (II) Administrative support: R.K and A.J, (III) Provision of study materials or patients: R.K, (IV) Collection and assembly of data: A.J, (V) Data analysis and interpretation: R.K, A.J, (VI) Manuscript writing: All authors, (VII) Final approval of manuscript: All authors

Acknowledgments

We thank Dr. Cristian Smerdou (Cima Universidad de Navarra, Spain) and PD.Dr. Vladimir Temchura, Institute of Clinical and Molecular Virology, Friedrich-Alexander-University Erlangen-Nürnberg, 91054 Erlangen, Germany for valuable help. We thank the Zahedan University of Medical Sciences, Zahedan, Iran for providing sera from recovered COVID-19 patients.

References:

1. Krammer, F., *SARS-CoV-2 vaccines in development*. *Nature*, 2020. **586**(7830): p. 516-527.
2. Ye, T., et al., *Current status of COVID-19 (pre) clinical vaccine development*. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, 2020. **59**(43): p. 18885-18897.
3. Klasse, P., D.F. Nixon, and J.P. Moore, *Immunogenicity of clinically relevant SARS-CoV-2 vaccines in nonhuman primates and humans*. *Science advances*, 2021. **7**(12): p. eabe8065.
4. Löwik, D.W. and J.C. van Hest, *Peptide based amphiphiles*. *Chemical Society Reviews*, 2004. **33**(4): p. 234-245.
5. Zhao, X., et al., *Molecular self-assembly and applications of designer peptide amphiphiles*. *Chemical Society Reviews*, 2010. **39**(9): p. 3480-3498.
6. Matson, J.B., R.H. Zha, and S.I. Stupp, *Peptide self-assembly for crafting functional biological materials*. *Current Opinion in Solid State and Materials Science*, 2011. **15**(6): p. 225-235.
7. Kushnir, N., S.J. Streatfield, and V. Yusibov, *Virus-like particles as a highly efficient vaccine platform: diversity of targets and production systems and advances in clinical development*. *Vaccine*, 2012. **31**(1): p. 58-83.
8. Karch, C.P. and P. Burkhard, *Vaccine technologies: From whole organisms to rationally designed protein assemblies*. *Biochemical pharmacology*, 2016. **120**: p. 1-14.
9. López-Sagasetta, J., et al., *Self-assembling protein nanoparticles in the design of vaccines*. *Computational and structural biotechnology journal*, 2016. **14**: p. 58-68.
10. Durier, C., et al., *Clinical safety of HIV lipopeptides used as vaccines in healthy volunteers and HIV-infected adults*. *Aids*, 2006. **20**(7): p. 1039-1049.
11. Schmidt, J., et al., *Intratumoural injection of the toll-like receptor-2/6 agonist 'macrophage-activating lipopeptide-2' in patients with pancreatic carcinoma: a phase I/II trial*. *British journal of cancer*, 2007. **97**(5): p. 598-604.
12. Hamley, I.W., *Lipopeptides for vaccine development*. *Bioconjugate Chemistry*, 2021. **32**(8): p. 1472-1490.
13. Stern, L.J. and D.C. Wiley, *Antigenic peptide binding by class I and class II histocompatibility proteins*. *Structure*, 1994. **2**(4): p. 245-251.
14. Keikha, R., S.M. Hashemi-Shahri, and A. Jebali, *The evaluation of novel oral vaccines based on self-amplifying RNA lipid nanoparticles (saRNA LNPs), saRNA transfected Lactobacillus plantarum LNPs, and saRNA transfected Lactobacillus plantarum to neutralize SARS-CoV-2 variants alpha and delta*. *Scientific Reports*, 2021. **11**(1): p. 21308.

15. Costantini, V.P., et al., *Humoral and mucosal immune responses to human norovirus in the elderly*. *The Journal of infectious diseases*, 2020. **221**(11): p. 1864-1874.
16. Lu, B.L., G.M. Williams, and M.A. Brimble, *TLR2 agonists and their structure–activity relationships*. *Organic & biomolecular chemistry*, 2020. **18**(27): p. 5073-5094.
17. Abudula, T., et al., *Supramolecular Self-Assembled Peptide-Based Vaccines: Current State and Future Perspectives*, *Front. Chem.* 8 (2020). 2020.
18. Singh, M. and D. O'Hagan, *Advances in vaccine adjuvants*. *Nature biotechnology*, 1999. **17**(11): p. 1075-1081.
19. Hu, H.-G. and Y.-M. Li, *Emerging adjuvants for cancer immunotherapy*. *Frontiers in Chemistry*, 2020. **8**: p. 601.
20. Azmi, F., et al., *Recent progress in adjuvant discovery for peptide-based subunit vaccines*. *Human vaccines & immunotherapeutics*, 2014. **10**(3): p. 778-796.
21. Chauhan, G., et al., *Nanotechnology for COVID-19: therapeutics and vaccine research*. *ACS nano*, 2020. **14**(7): p. 7760-7782.
22. Poland, G.A., I.G. Ovsyannikova, and R.B. Kennedy, *SARS-CoV-2 immunity: review and applications to phase 3 vaccine candidates*. *The Lancet*, 2020. **396**(10262): p. 1595-1606.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.